

NEWS SELECTION CRITERIA ONTV

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Abstract: Television, as a powerful and universal tool, plays a significant role in covering the events that happen every moment in the world. What is happening in the world around us, all these events are not covered by the media. Rather, there are values, elements and factors that make the media have criteria for selecting and covering events.

This research was conducted with the aim of investigating the same criteria that play a role in selecting news in the television media. The method used in this research has a review form and the topics have been analyzed and analyzed using the tools of books and scientific articles. In the theoretical basis of this article, two practical theories in the field of communication (theory of framing and the theory of gatekeeping) are used, and in the analysis and analysis of the issues, the theory of social responsibility is also used.

What was obtained in the findings of this issue shows that the television media and those involved in these media consider external and internal factors more than news values and elements in selecting the news they cover. And in some events, neglecting external and internal factors in the selection of news may cause a media to stop publishing. What was obtained in the findings of this issue shows that the television media and those involved in these media consider external and internal factors more than news values and elements in selecting the news they cover. And in some events, neglecting external and internal factors in the selection of news may cause a media to stop publishing. And this is the reason why the media with professional tactics in the selection and coverage of world events have the most trust and satisfaction of their audience, but the media that cannot overcome this problem, usually the level of trust and satisfaction and even The benefit of their audience is low and they face serious problems.

Keywords: television, news, selection, gatekeeping, framing, social responsibility, audience.

Introduction

The media, especially television, has been playing an inclusive role in the society for a long time. It has gained an important position in the society by producing programs, broadcasting news and serials; As far as in this time with the Internet and

social media networks, you can find few families that do not use television. This means of communication plays a significant role in the direction of public opinion.

News, as the main meaning of the existence of this media, adds more to the power of this media. Audiences turn to television in order to be aware of the events of their environment, and even to fill their free time. Referring to a media address to use and benefit from, in order to meet informational needs, provides the context of persuasion, satisfaction and trust. The trust and satisfaction of the audience is considered an asset for the media, which is not possible without professional activities and the selection of correct and professional criteria in covering news events.

In this article, the types of news structures along with the selection criteria and the pressures on the news gatekeepers have been discussed. On the other hand, the media have a responsibility towards their audience to strictly refrain from covering events that are not only not needed by their audience, but are harmful to the society and the audience.

Statement of the problem

How to choose news events and how to cover these events is the most important concern of information consumers. The main problem that caused this article to be written as a review is to examine and understand the same criteria for selecting news using books and scientific articles, of course, by analyzing and analyzing some events that are covered by the media and it is clearly understandable that The facts of those events are not told at all, and if they are told, they are left in the margins.

In the society we live in, a smaller percentage of people have the blessing of media literacy. Therefore, they hardly understand which audience is which news program from which media. Even those educated in the field of journalism sometimes make a mistake in identifying which event was selected on what basis.

It is difficult to know how professional and ethical principles and rules in the selection of news events are considered by the media or to what extent they are observed. It is a difficult task and requires research. The factors that can force the operators and gatekeepers of news in a TV media to choose and select news to find media coverage are also not easy to understand, in this field, research and study must be done carefully. For this purpose, this review article has been done using books and scientific articles that were written on this matter, so that the understanding of this issue becomes a little easier.

The importance and necessity of research

In the current situation, whether we like it or not, we are consumers of media information. One of the most watched media is television. Television, as a capable medium in the era of the Internet and high-speed media of virtual networks, still has high value and importance to its audience. Television news programs are still watched

by the audience in most of the Afghan families and television is considered the most important source of news for these families.

The multiplicity of events, with different coverage by different televisions, confuses the audience, and the audience cannot distinguish good from bad, lies from reality, main events from marginal or low-value events... Therefore, researching and solving this issue is considered an urgent necessity for the television audience in our society and is of great importance. This issue can help in understanding a social concern.

The media, which considers the priority in the news selection criterion of the interests and interests of the society, to be separated into the media whose financial and political interests prevail over social responsibilities. In this research, there has been some clarification and rooting in this field.

Research purposes

The main purpose of this research is to investigate the selection criteria of news and by which criteria a news can be highlighted and marginalized in the media of television.

Some of the objectives of this research are: Examining the professional criteria in news selection, the extent of censorship of facts and factors can play a role in the censorship of facts in a media, the way news events are framed is to preserve social interests and interests and vice versa.

The theoretical framework of research

1. Goalkeeping theory

It is a fact that only part of the news and information reaches the audience. There is a process that for some reason does not allow large parts of reality to be covered by the media. Censoring, removing, adding and even adjusting, highlighting or marginalizing news events is a common thing in the media, especially in television news channels. The person or people who plays a role in filtering information and news and allows what news and how to be published, or what news should not be published for what reason, are gatekeepers. Gatekeeping starts from the point where the communication operator creates or discovers information. Information reaches communication organizations from a diverse range of channels. These channels are classified into three categories: official, unofficial and innovative. Conventional and informal channels of information bring the outside world into a communication organization, where an organizational border guard makes the first decision about whether this information enters or leaves the channel. There may be billions of messages that receive the attention of communication actors, but Most of them will never pass through the first gate as follows:

Some goalkeepers may be influenced by the actions of the goalkeepers before them. Some messages clearly have more news value than other messages and we know that the more news value a message has, the more likely it will pass through a news gate. (Shoemaker, 2012: 5). The question is what kind of information is most newsworthy. There is a long list of news values, such as: recency, proximity, importance, impact or consequence, interest, conflict or collision, controversy, prominence, strangeness, and unconventionality.

Wilbur Schramm says: "No aspect of communication is more striking than the large number of choices and rejections that must be made to create the right symbol in the minds of the sender and the receiver." Kurt Levin first used the term "gatekeeper". This concept provided a framework for leading communication scientists to evaluate the selection process and say why some news items are selected and others are rejected. According to this theory, gatekeeping is a tool to identify the way to create extensive social changes in a society by one person.

Attitudes, working procedures of communication activists, organizational levels, levels of social system, levels of social analysis and institutions, propaganda of interest groups, looking at the variables of ideology and culture, can also have an impact on the way of event gating. (ibid.: 4).

News values can also be a criterion for passing the gate to enter the coverage of events. Factors such as ad owners, interest groups, public relations, other competing or cooperating media are not without influence in the decision of the gatekeepers in the selection of news events. Gatekeepers or controllers of information flows operate according to principles and regulations that allow or prohibit the entry of certain information into broadcast coverage, which the audience can or cannot access. Based

on the conducted research, sometimes the goalkeeping is affected by the amount of social control. (Tavakli, 1390: 105)

Third world countries, due to the disparities in media facilities and the lack of specialized and efficient communication forces, high illiteracy statistics, economic disparities, weak management in the fields of planning and coordination, most of their non-native news is provided through the media and major global news agencies. This itself provides the context of dependence to receive information. Affiliates are more and more quickly influenced by media power, and as a result, these audiences are more likely to fall victim to the decision-making and gatekeeping of news that has received targeted and categorized media coverage. (Afkhami et al., 1387: 11).

Framing theory

Usually, the media workers in covering news events frame the news under the specific policy and criteria of the same media and make it available to their audience. News framing is actually a decision on how to package and structure news that contains messages and goals for the audience of the same media. Based on this structure, news gatekeepers decide which parts of a news story should be covered for their audience. Framing and its concept in the field of communication and journalism was first proposed by Gitlin in 1977-1980. News framing is considered by communication experts to be the central idea of the organizer or the trajectory of a news report. According to Tankard, framing is rooted in the process of selection, emphasis, exception and description of the news through the news organization. (Zablizadeh, 1392: 124) In the framing of news, two basic issues can be noted. "Being a model" and "selectivity". A communication discussion relates the framing theory to the news selection criteria in the media. Just as in the theory of filtering, the gatekeeper person or people decide what content is allowed to be covered and what content does not pass through the filter, in the framing theory, these same people decide how and in what format an event is covered. Which topics should be highlighted in an event and which other topics should be reflected in the margins of events. Framing theory refers to the process of organizing the truth by classifying events in certain ways, emphasizing some aspects of them more than others, and deciding on the meaning of an event and how it happened. Any presentation of the truth, even if they have the necessary balance, is still associated with some kind of framing. That is, framing is associated with selection, emphasis and exclusion. The words journalists use, the narrative structure of the event, the facts they include or exclude from the story, and the people they quote all help to shape the event in a particular way. (Furqani and Nikkhah, 1392: 7). These frameworks are more visible in news reports and soft news. The tone of speech and images in news and television reports are considered clear examples of framing. Framing is actually two steps after gatekeeping. First, the gatekeeper decides whether or not to broadcast an event, and if the news is approved for broadcast, it is decided whether or not to

highlight the issue, and finally whether or not to highlight certain aspects of it. (Ibid.: 8). Adjusting the content of the news is a careful and considered work. In the past, there was a belief that the news can convey the events objectively to the audience, but numerous media researches regarding the content of the news showed that absolute objectivity in the regulation of the news is not possible in practice; To the extent that some consider the news as a "reflection of the interests of the media owners". In the sense that what is taken into account in the regulation of news are the interests, wishes and views of the media owners rather than the event that happened in the surrounding world. Events that contain relatively high news value do not get the opportunity to be mentioned in the media (Zablizadeh, 126:1392). With the passage of time, more evidence was provided for this point of view that the media do not start presenting topics without bias, but each of them, depending on the policy of their news organization, adjusts it in a special way and exposes a certain topic more to the audience. These evidences finally led to the formulation of message framing theory, which emphasized replacing messages in predetermined frames. Based on this, recruitment takes place in a three-step process; The first stage, which is actually related to the formation of these patterns in the media, is called "framing" in which the frames are considered as dependent variables that internal and external factors affect their formation. In the second stage, there is the identification of frames in the news, for which two general and topic-oriented types can be imagined, and in the third stage, the different effects of framing on the audience are related. This process is depicted in the form of the following figure.

The first stage in framing refers to the factors that affect the structural features of the news frame. The framing process takes place in the continuous interaction between journalists, elites and social movements. The result of the framing process is the

appearance of this frame in the text. The second stage is related to the time when the frames appear in the news. In this section, the frameworks have appeared in two general forms, subject-oriented and general. Topic frameworks are linked to specific topics and events. Generic frameworks transcend thematic limitations and can be identified in relation to various topics. Even some of them are placed in different cultural situations beyond time. In the last stage, the framing process reaches the audience. (ibid: 127-128).

Conceptual review of the topic

1. Selectivity

In the field of communication and journalism, selection is the selection of events that happen in the society by the responsible manager and reporter for publishing and broadcasting according to the influence of internal and external factors in a media. Or the news that reaches the media has passed through many channels and a long way. Some of these gates are open, some are half-open, and some are completely closed, and the media is the last selector who decides whether this news or content should be communicated to the people through its media! In the news selection of journalists, reporters who go in search of news and they prepare it, they play an essential role. At this stage, they evaluate some news as presentable and some as unpresentable. Other factors also play a role in the selectivity or choice of news in the way of coverage and non-coverage, whose judgments make events stand out or stop. Both issues have been discussed in detail in the theories of research and framing.

2. Television

Television is one of the tools of mass communication; which provides the possibility of transmitting sound and image simultaneously through very short radio waves and, along with repeater and amplifier devices, it makes it possible to send sound and image to distant places.

The word television is derived from the Greek word "Tele" meaning "far" and the Latin word "Vision" meaning vision. According to this, television means "viewing from a distance", on this basis it can be said that television is "a means of communication for broadcasting and receiving moving images and sounds from a distance" after radio and television, it has become an audio and video network in the advanced societies of the world. And soon it achieved extensive global progress (Habib; 50: 1393). Television is a powerful medium with a large audience around the world, especially in third world countries. Television, as the most important source of news, plays an essential role in covering the events around its audience. Therefore, what is covered as news for its audience is important, how it is selected and what criteria are considered for selecting and covering the news. It is obvious that the news selection criteria are not the same in all TV news channels, but according to the

conditions, the type of audience, the external and internal factors of the same TV channel, the news selection criteria are different.

3. Audience

The concept of audience can be mentioned in this article because the media news is for the audience. The audience is the consumer of information that is covered through television news channels.

The word "audience" has become a common term in the process of mass communication for a long time to the extent that media managers and media theorists have the same understanding of the word "audience" and its use by media users who recognize this word as an unambiguous description of themselves is common. However, the word audience, behind its popular usage, is full of differences in meaning, misunderstandings, and theoretical differences. The above problems mainly arise from the fact that the simple and single word of the audience is used to refer to a reality that is becoming more and more complex and diverse.

What is presented in a more comprehensive definition of the audience is that; The audience simply refers to the readers, viewers, listeners of one of the media channels or any content and show (McQuail, 2010: 8).

4. Social responsibility

One of the most important criteria that should not be forgotten in the selection of news events for television channels is the responsibility of the media towards society. Indeed, coverage of important events with complete impartiality and accuracy. The media should adhere to their duties and social obligations. Based on this point of view, the theory of social responsibility was proposed and developed. Based on the theory of social responsibility, the media, in addition to providing information, entertainment and sales, should cause the acquisition of votes and grow discussions and important words that are worth saying.

According to this theory, the media is controlled by the consumer's actions, society's opinions and professional ethics. This theory always considers the independence of the media with commitment to the society. (Sorin and Tankard, 2012: 445).

5. News

News is a word that is lexically taken from the Arabic language and is equivalent to the European word information. The most contemporary use of the word "news" in specialized journalism is information. (Bashir, 33:1392) In itself, any new information about an event can be news, but not all events can be worth media coverage and become a media news. In order for an event to be allowed to be covered in a media, there are criteria for choosing a few news from among tens, hundreds and maybe thousands of events around us. These criteria can be used in different ways, for example; News values, news elements, interests and interests of media members, policy owners,

advertisement owners, and other external and internal factors should play a key role in choosing and turning an event into media news.

Although many scientists in the field of communication spoke and wrote their opinions to define news, but what is covered in the media and television news channels for their audience is the least amount of truth from the definition that exists in the definitions of books from the point of view of scientists. Several definitions of news have been quoted: News is a report of reality, but not every reality can be called news. Or the news is a message that has the possibility of being true or false. And likewise, news is an event that has "news value" for one person or group, but for another or another group it may be unimportant (Badiei et al., 1383: 19).

6. Variety of news fields

The diversity of the news field can also give criteria to the audience to determine what news should be published and what news should not be published, or which news should be considered valuable and which news should be considered insignificant. Diversity in the field of news can include; Special news, general news, national news, international news, positive news, negative news, confidential news, non-confidential news, hard news and soft news. Each of these areas has definitions and explanations that can play a role in choosing and selecting events as media coverage based on their explanations. Paying attention to news coverage and news flow can also be another basic criterion in the selection of news events. News streaming is the targeted production and dissemination of news. In fact, news streaming is a discourse and software approach in relation to the production and dissemination of news. Today, the major news agencies are trying to develop news and information institutions globally and to break their exclusivity. In addition to these criteria, concepts such as accuracy of news, clarity of news, comprehensiveness of news, attention to news values, which are the most important (inclusion, reputation, encounters, differences, conflict and conflict, exceptions and surprises, magnitude and abundance, spiritual and geographical proximity) and so on. It can be the criteria for selecting an event for media coverage. These criteria, which alone or sometimes by combining with each other, create an event that does not exist in the nature of the event itself. The criteria of news value often help the reporter in searching and understanding the news (subject finding). And it also helps the gatekeepers and selectors of news events to be prioritized and exploited as criteria for comparison in valuing and selecting events. (Badiei et al., 2013:20).

Research Methodology

Methodology in research is actually the process of how to collect information and evidence and turn them into findings in order to achieve knowledge and truth that the researcher has determined as the goal of his research. This article is a review article that has been discussed with the library method or the collection and analysis of the

issues of compilation. The tools used in this research are books, scientific articles, and other documents and evidence that help in the analysis and analysis of scientific issues. Using the sources of scientific books and articles with the spiritual preservation of the author and mentioning the source, and using the definitions and quotations of experts in the field of communication and journalism, while compiling the criteria for selecting news events in the mentioned sources, according to the social audience analyzed and analysis has been done.

Research findings

All the events of the world around us, without a doubt, do not have the capacity to be covered in the media. Among them, the news is selected with specific criteria. The selection of news events in television channels is usually accompanied by criteria that are many and different. The multiplicity of criteria means that each TV channel makes a decision in selecting news according to the policy, geographical location, values that are hidden in a news, news elements, decision-making factors from inside and outside the organization, media interests, etc. And different in the sense that, each media according to the area of broadcast coverage, the nature of their audience, the nature of the news programs they have, the amount of viewers of the news programs, the level of professional performance in the selection of events, paying attention to gaining the satisfaction and trust of the audience, the nature of orientation, criteria Prioritization of news, compliance with professional principles and ethical principles in selecting events, favorable dealings of those involved, financial and political affiliations, attention to social needs, etc., have different criteria for selecting news events and follow them. One of the important responsibilities of news media is to provide correct information to the audience. Ensuring the correctness of information that is given media coverage is one of the essentials of journalism and one of the basic principles in this profession. The criteria for selecting news events in a media should be such that the news of the events is covered as it happened, not as the gatekeepers or other agents and decision makers wanted it to happen. Professional standards of journalism require that the news of the events that are allowed to be covered should be comprehensive. Taking into account inappropriate and incorrect criteria in the selection and coverage of news events causes the graph of satisfaction and trust of the media audience to have a downward trend.

Conclusion

The media, especially television, choose to cover environmental events. This selection is done by media watchers with specific criteria. It is obvious that not all events can be covered by the media, only a part of this information reaches the audience. Information processing involves selecting parts of information to transmit and rejecting the rest. Gating or selection in news events starts from the point where the communication activist creates or discovers information. Information reaches

communication organizations from a diverse range of channels. These channels are classified into three categories: official, unofficial and innovative. Regular and informal channels of information bring the outside world to a communication organization, where an organizational boundary guard makes the first decision about the entry or exit of this information in the channel. There may be billions of messages that receive the attention of communication activists, but the majority of them will never get past the first gate. After the stage of filtering and selecting events and information, the stage of framing events and information comes. At this stage, it is decided which options of news events are placed and highlighted in the context of media coverage, and which parts of the information are placed on the sidelines and receive less attention from the audience. At this stage, exactly what the gatekeeper of the events realizes is his responsibility towards the society and he must realize his social responsibility. Paying attention to the social responsibility of media coverage of events results in increasing the level of satisfaction and trust of the audience towards the desired media. The trust of the audience is an asset for the media that no media can ignore.

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